

**Commentary on *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025,
“the first brachypterous stag beetle in Eurasia”, with proposition
of synonymy with *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819**

Cheng-Bin Wang¹, Jun-Jie Liu², Tian-Long He³

¹Engineering Research Center for Forest and Grassland Disaster Prevention and Reduction, Mianyang Normal University

166 Mianxing West Road, Mianyang 621000, Sichuan Province, China

e-mail: entomologist@qq.com

ORCID 0000-0002-7913-8779

²School of Artificial Intelligence and Big Data, Chongqing City University of Science and Technology,

Chongqing, 400000, China

e-mail: 3282852131@qq.com

ORCID 0009-0007-7492-0183

³Donghuaxincheng, Wangfenggang, Xiejiaji District, Huainan 232046, Anhui Province, China

e-mail: htl1988@qq.com

ORCID 0000-0001-7301-5105

Key words: Coleoptera, Lucanidae, taxonomy, new synonym, new combination.

Abstract. *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819 = *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, **syn. n.**, and *Nigidius sinensis* (Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025), **comb. n.**

On 11 December 2025 an article entitled “The first discovery of brachypterous stag beetle in Eurasia: A remarkable new genus and species of the tribe Figulini Burmeister, 1847 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae: Lucaninae) from southwestern China” was published online in *Zootaxa*. The paper described an impressive and sensational new species, *Geonigidius sinensis* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, which was assigned to the newly erected genus *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025.

The authors repeatedly asserted that brachyptery constitutes a first record for Eurasian Lucanidae: in Abstract “Despite centuries of active research on Eurasian Lucanidae, the absence of species with vestigial hindwings has remained a significant knowledge gap.”,

Cheng-Bin Wang, Jun-Jie Liu, Tian-Long He

on page 531 “Notably, no such case had been discovered in continental Eurasia before this study, ...”, and on page 546 “this trait remains notably unreported from Eurasian species.” The unpublished data of these authors, however, appear to be incomplete. The condition of atrophied hindwings has previously been observed or inferred in certain Eurasian lucanid lineages, as listed below.

***Aegus hikidai* Araya, 1994**

Araya, 1994: title “Discovery of a flightless *Aegus* (Coleoptera, Lucanidae) in Borneo”, 271 “... a female of the genus *Aegus* with atrophied wings ...”, 273 “Hindwings (Fig. 2) very short and atrophied, 0.52 times the elytral length (about 3.2 mm in length);”, 278 “Atrophied wings and firmly interlocked elytra are also its unique characteristics shared by no other species in the genus.”, 278 “... the atrophied wings of *A. hikidai* are very short (0.52 times the elytral length).”

Fujita 2010: 331 “後翅が退化した特異なネプトクワガタ。 [A peculiar *Aegus* whose hindwings are reduced.]”.

***Aegus inaharai* Fujita, 2010**

Fujita, 2010: 330 “次種のムルハネナシネプトと同様に後翅が退化した種と思われる, [Like the following species *Aegus hikidai*, this species is thought to have atrophied hindwings.]”.

***Nigidius sticheri* Okuda et Fukinuki, 2000**

Fujita 2010: 408 “小さく、基方が狭まった上翅の形態から、本種は後翅が退化しているか、ほとんど飛翔しない種の可能性がある。 [Based on the small, basally narrowed shape of the elytra, this species likely has atrophied hindwings or is a species that rarely flies.]”.

In addition, the justification offered for erection of the genus *Geonigidius* is insufficiently robust. The authors placed primary emphasis on brachyptery, treating it as a decisive generic character; for example they stated on page 546 that “As brachyptery generally remains stable within genera, it serves as a reliable generic-level character.” This reliance is misplaced. The suite of characters that

Cheng-Bin Wang, Jun-Jie Liu, Tian-Long He

distinguish *G. sinensis* from members of *Nigidius*, including the four characters in the identification key and the nine diagnostic differences listed in the Diagnosis, are best interpreted as autapomorphies of a specialised species rather than as synapomorphies that would justify recognition of a separate genus. Erecting a monotypic genus on the basis of such derived, apparently species-level modifications is arbitrary and tenuous. On the basis of the foregoing considerations, the following new subjective synonymy is proposed: *Nigidius* Macleay, 1819 = *Geonigidius* Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025, **syn. n.** The type species is transferred accordingly as *Nigidius sinensis* (Xin, Gong, Zhong & Qi, 2025), **comb. n.**

This proposal is advanced to encourage further critical assessment of generic limits within the Figulini and to promote careful evaluation of character polarity before the establishment of new genera.

Acknowledgements. We are indebted to Chang-Chin Chen (Tianjin, China), Hao Huang (Qingdao, China), Hao Xu (Mianyang Normal University, China), Bi-Sheng Zhan (Zhenjiang, China) and Zhi-Hong Zhan (Nanjing Agricultural University, China) for their considerable help in this study. We thank two anonymous reviewers for their constructive comments on earlier versions of the manuscript. This study was self-funded by the authors.

REFERENCES

- Araya K 1994: Discovery of a flightless *Aegus* (Coleoptera, Lucanidae) in Borneo. *Elytra*, 22 (2): 271–280.
- Fujita H 2010: *The Lucanid Beetles of the World. Mushi-Sha's Iconographic Series of Insects 6*. Mushi-Sha, Tokyo, 472 pp., 248 pls.
- Xin F-Y, Gong J-X, Zhong X-T & Qi Z-H 2025: The first discovery of brachypterous stag beetle in Eurasia: A remarkable new genus and species of the tribe Figulini Burmeister, 1847 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae: Lucaninae) from southwestern China. *Zootaxa*, 5728 (3): 531–548. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5728.3.4>

Received: 24.12.2025

Accepted: 25.02.2026